

Polytheistic Pre-Islamic South Arabia

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Entry tags: Arabian Religions, Religious Group

Although the Bronze Age in ancient South Arabia (modern-day Yemen) is still poorly understood, there is a wealth of archaeological and epigraphic data for reconstructing the region's history from the beginning of the first millennium BCE onward. While epigraphs in the Ancient South Arabian script may date as early as the 11th century BCE, texts useful to reconstructing South Arabian history and religion only truly begin to emerge from the 8th century BCE onward. These epigraphs attest to a plurality of peoples and city-states who worshipped a variety of gods. Most important among these are the four kingdoms, Saba, Maʿīn, Qataban, and Ḥaḍramawt, the former three which occupied the western highlands of Yemen while the latter was concentrated further east along Wadi Ḥaḍramawt. Each of these kingdoms had its own language (Sabaic, Minaic, Qatabanic, Ḥaḍramitic) and religion, which consisted in worship of the common high god ʿAttar in addition to a kingdom's own patron deity (Almaqah for Saba, Wadd for Maʿīn, ʿAmm for Qataban, and Sin for Ḥaḍramawt) and a national pantheon of lesser gods. The influence of South Arabian religion was not restricted to modern-day Yemen. As early as 700 BCE, Sabaic epigraphs, gods, and religious architecture appear in northeast Africa. This eventually disappears in the second half of the first millennium BCE, a time during which other South Arabian kingdoms notably began to expand. Ḥaḍramawt then ventured eastward into modern-day Oman, where it founded a trading port at modern Khor Rori south of Salalah in the Dhofar. In the western South Arabian highlands, a new kingdom called Ḥimyar emerged. Over the next centuries, these Ḥimyarites would gradually increase their influence until they finally conquered all of South Arabia in the late third/early fourth century CE. Under their hegemony, state-sponsored polytheism continued until at least 360 CE, to which the latest known polytheistic text dates. Following this, South Arabia adopted a new monotheistic religion, resulting in the polytheistic gods disappearing from the epigraphic record.

Date Range: 800 BCE - 360 CE

Region: Ancient South Arabia and its peripheries

Region tags: Asia, Western Asia, Oman, Yemen, Africa, Eastern Africa, Eritrea, Ethiopia

A map of Ancient South Arabia as attested by inscriptional finds.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Inter-tribal conflict could be viewed religiously. The 8th century BCE text DAI Širwāḥ 2005-50 identifies the Sabaeans as the "Children of Almaqah," who was their patron god. They fight against the Qatabanians, identified as the "Children of 'Amm," Qataban's national god.

Similarly, in the 7th century BCE inscription RES 3945, the Sabaean king assigns territory to Qataban. He portrays this as giving land to two of their gods, 'Amm and 'Anby. Hence, inter-tribal conflict could be portrayed as gods losing or gaining power.

Reference: Ahmed Fahkry. *An archaeological Journey to Yemen (March-May 1947)*. Cairo: Government Press.

Reference: DAI Şirwāḥ 2005-50

Reference: RES 3945

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Notably, the Romans unsuccessfully invaded the region under Aelius Gallus in 25 BC.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Religious identification is most connected to tribe and locality of an individual.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While there are oracles from the gods that are held as authoritative in various localities, there are no known corpora of literature that were circulated and revered more broadly.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Tombs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Thrones

Reference: Michael Jung. A short review of Southern Arabian thrones and stone furniture.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– Some public spaces

Notes: Many apotropaic amulets engraved with "Wadd is Father" have been found, which would have been worn to ward off evil.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Notes: Eyes were frequently carved alongside names on stelae to represent deceased individuals. These stelae began as minimalistic depictions that could also include other parts of the face, such as the nose and hair. During the later periods, depictions of the dead would stylistically develop into more complex and fully-detailed carvings of not just the individual's face but also their body.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Sacred places frequently use art of animals such as ibexes, bulls, lions, ostriches and sometimes even Mischwesen (sphinxes, griffins, and lamassus). However, it is often unclear whether these represent merely the presence of the divine or the god or goddess themselves. A clear example of zoomorphic representation of divinities is CIH 458, where three divine members of the Sabaeen pantheon are represented by ibexes.

Reference: Christian Robin. Qatabān (royaume de l'Arabie méridionale antique) et son grand dieu 'Amm.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Generally, anthropomorphic representations are rare in South Arabia. However, two pillars from the 8th century BC were unearthed in a temple in Nashshan that depicted anthropomorphic pairs of gods facing each other. Bronze images of possibly the Greek gods Mars (BM 122021) and Aphrodite (BM 130901) have been unearthed, in addition to a local deity named the "Lord of the Sanctuary" (Bron 1999).

Reference: Sabina Antonini de Maigret. South Arabian Religious Iconography: The Language of Symbols and the Representation of Deities. (Isabelle Sachet, Ed.), Dieux et déesses d'Arabie: Images et représentations. Paris: De Boccard. isbn: 9782701803067 2701803063.

Reference: Bron 1999

Reference: BM 130901

Reference: BM 122021

Reference: Mounir Arbach , Rémy Audouin , Christian Robin. La découverte du temple d'Aranyada' à Nashān et la chronologie des Labu'ides.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: The most notable examples of this are 'Athtar dhu-Qabḏ, a Minaean manifestation of the high-god 'Athtar, who is represented by a "door" (or possibly an oxhide ingot) and the Sabaean patron god Almaqah, who is represented by a curved implement ("Totschläger").

Reference: Sabina Antonini de Maigret. South Arabian Religious Iconography: The Language of Symbols and the Representation of Deities. (Isabelle Sachet, Ed.), Dieux et déesses d'Arabie: Images et représentations. Paris: De Boccard. isbn: 9782701803067 2701803063.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals are frequently displayed on their funerary stelae, which may

represented their deceased state.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Astral imagery, frequently constellations of circles, are used as well.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The word for "self, soul" (nfs¹) is also used for a person's funerary stela. This might imply that the individual has a continued presence at the location of their grave.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Valuable items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Incense altars

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: At a Minaean necropolis at Baraqish, bones were not found in the tombs, which led Antonini and Agostini to hypothesize that the tombs might function as cenotaphs. Albeit, this is still theoretical.

Reference: Sabina Antonini , Alessio Agostini undefined. A Minaean necropolis at Barāqish (Jawf, Republic of Yemen). Preliminary report of the 2005-2006 archaeological campaigns. Rome: ISIAO.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: There are actually two supreme high gods present in South Arabia: 'Athtar and 'Īl, the latter who is the traditional West Semitic head of the pantheon. These two deities appear together at the top of pillars from the temple of 'Aranyada' in Nashshan, indicating that they are of a higher rank than the other gods depicted below them. In fact, 'Īl even is mentioned before 'Athtar in the inscription Haram 5/3, implying that he might be superior. However, direct references to 'Īl fall out by the 6th century BCE, with his last possible mention in RES 3943/4, albeit he is indirectly referred to as a progenitor with the mention of the minor goddesses called the "Daughters of 'Īl." There is also a possible "Clan of 'Īl" in the untranslated minuscule oracular requests (L 019/2, Mon.script.sab. 76/2), which contains several lower-ranking gods who might be considered 'Īl's offspring. By contrast, 'Athtar functions as the high god throughout all of Arabia and is frequently the object of devotion.

Reference: RES 3943

Reference: Haram 5

Reference: Christian Robin. Les "filles du Dieu" de Saba' à la Mecque: réflexions sur l'agencement des panthéons dans l'Arabie ancienne.

Reference: Mounir Arbach , Rémy Audouin , Christian Robin. La découverte du temple d'Aranyada' à Nashān et la chronologie des Labu'ides.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: At the temple of Aranyada' in Nashshān, at the top of two pillars 'Athtar is depicted standing across from the other Semitic high-god 'Īl. These two gods are standing, holding staves, and wearing heavy robes. Within South Arabia, this is an extraordinary instance as generally deities are depicted by symbolic and non-anthropomorphic forms.

Reference: Mounir Arbach , Rémy Audouin , Christian Robin. La découverte du temple d'Aranyada' à Nashān et la chronologie des Labu'ides.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: 'Athtar can provide the rain, like other South Arabian deities, but is not explicitly connected with the sky.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: 'Athtar may have a connection with the underworld but it is indefinite. Near the end of the polytheistic period, 'Athtar Sharīqān is invoked to protect funerary monuments from destruction; however, other buildings such as cisterns and houses are entrusted to this god as well. In earlier times, a funerary statue issues an oracle in a temple of 'Athtar (M 375), which may hint at a chthonic affiliation with the god.

Reference: M 375

Reference: RES 4090

The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: 'Athtar is said to have an oracle in Haram 13, by which an individual who commits violence can be exposed. In CIH 456, an individual petitions 'Athtar to make known the person who murdered his father.

Reference: CIH 456

Reference: Haram 13

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: 'Athtar is frequently petitioned for protection against disaster and destruction.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is very little attestation of dream oracles. The few instances that are attested are for other gods but not for 'Athtar himself.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: A number of deities had names formed of two syntactical elements, which resembles the names of humans. Examples of these are 'Izazallāt "The Power of (the goddess) al-Lat," Laḥay'athat "Athtar Shines," and Sumūyada' "His name knew." Christian Robin hypothesizes that these names represent divinized ancestors. However, other explanations are also possible. For instance, some could be hypostatized attributes of the deity (compare the hypostatic "Wrath of Yahweh" in Biblical 2 Samuel 24:1, which incites David to do evil rather than Yahweh himself). Alternatively, these could possibly be the name of divinized physical entities or idols (such as the Minaic deity called "The Throne of Qabḏ").

Reference: Christian Robin. South Arabia, Religions in Pre-Islamic. (Jane McAuliffe Dammen, Ed.), Encyclopaedia of the Qur'ān. Leiden: Brill. isbn: 9004123563 9789004123564.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

Notes: A number of fantastical Mischwesen (sphinxes, griffins, lamassus) are depicted in South Arabian art. These most likely played a protective role.

Reference: Christian Robin. Les «anges»(shams) et autres êtres surnaturels d'apparence humaine dans l'Arabie antique. (Sara Kuehn , Stefan Leder , Hans-Peter Pökel, Ed.), The Intermediate Worlds of Angels: Islamic Representations of Celestial Beings in Transcultural Contexts. Beirut: Orient-Institut. isbn: 9783956506239 3956506235.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They are depicted in art but it is unclear if they could physically be seen.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the high god 'Athtar and the other lower-ranking deities, there were various types of demi-gods. These consisted in both the aforementioned non-human Mischwesen and a variety of minor deities. Early in South Arabian history, there were the "Daughters of 'Īl," a collection of low-ranking goddesses that were worshipped across the region. From the end of the first millennium BCE onward, a number of other types of demi-gods emerge. Two classes of tutelary deities called the Shams (literally "Sun (goddess)") and Rabī ("Protector") served to protect individuals and their lineages. There were also the manḍaḥ, sometimes translated as "genie," who protected buildings. Various minor harmful supernatural entities were also believed to exist, against whom individuals sought divine protection.

Reference: Christian Robin. Les «anges»(shams) et autres êtres surnaturels d'apparence humaine dans l'Arabie antique. (Sara Kuehn , Stefan Leder , Hans-Peter Pökel, Ed.), *The Intermediate Worlds of Angels: Islamic Representations of Celestial Beings in Transcultural Contexts*. Beirut: Orient-Institut. isbn: 9783956506239 3956506235.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: In two cases, deities appear to be ranked according to their lineage. At Balaq al-Janūbī the deity Hawbas is mentioned before an otherwise unknown "Son of Hawbas." There is also the "Clan of 'Īl" in a couple of untranslated miniscule oracular requests (L 019/2, Mon.script.sab. 76/2), which appears to contain several gods who seem to be considered the offspring of the high god 'Īl.

Reference: MAFRAY-al-Balaq al-Janūbī 9

Reference: MAFRAY-al-Balaq al-Janūbī 1

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Textually, higher ranking gods almost always are mentioned before lower ranking gods when a series of gods are invoked. Archaeologically, excavations at the temple of 'Aranyada' in Nashshan uncovered two engraved pillars. These pillars contained a series of vertically descending rows, which each had a pair of gods facing one another. The higher ranking gods were at the top of the pillar while the lower ranking gods were towards the bottom.

Reference: Mounir Arbach , Rémy Audouin , Christian Robin. *La découverte du temple d'Aranyada' à Nashān et la chronologie des Labu'ides*.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Male-gendered gods rank before female-gendered goddesses.

Notes: With few exceptions, gods of higher rank are mentioned before gods of lesser rank in lists of deities. In these cases, we see that every male deity is almost always invoked before every female deity in these lists.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: In MAFRAY-Darb aş-Şabī 32, the god Nakraḥ is said to command an individual to repent for some crimes that appear to involve murder. Elsewhere in the unpublished oracular request

Mon.script.sab 74, a god is asked a series of questions to determine who murdered a child-
assumedly because the deity in question was angered by it.

Reference: MAFRAY-Darb aṣ-Ṣabī 32

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Incest:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Yes [specify]: Intercourse is prohibited in certain cultic contexts. See the section on personal hygiene below.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Individuals will swear oaths to gods (gzm), implying that the gods were perceived to care about the oath's fulfillment.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Supernatural entities engage with sorcery by preventing it, such as in MṢ1/11. However, it divinities view sorcery positively or negatively on whole.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Reference: MŞ1

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Inscriptions concerning property construction and ownership normally invoke various deities.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Laws concerning fairness are usually issued by non-cultic judicial figures.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Ancient South Arabian texts exhibit a concern for personal hygiene in the form of sexual purity, wherein the act of sex or contact with sexual fluids were seen as defiling. At Haram, there are many records of individuals repenting for introducing a contaminant into the sanctuary's sacred spaces. This could be as brazen as having sex inside the temple itself or during sacred times (FB-wādī Shuḍayf 2; Haram 34; Haram 40). A woman's period could also defile sacred space (al-Şilwī 3) as also would unclean clothing (MŞM 7250; Haram 35; Haram

40). Men were also not supposed to wash semen off in the sanctuary's well (al-Şilwī 1, FB-wādī Shuḍayf 2). Outside of Haram, at the Minaean capital Ma'īn, an oracle from the god Wadd (RES 2803) was engraved on the gate, which prohibited fornicators from entering. At Marib, there was a similar concern, with MB 2005 I-88 prohibiting sexual intercourse and impurity caused by sexual intercourse inside Almaqah's temple. An unprovenanced bronze pendant München 94-317880 explicitly depicts a couple having intercourse and serves as a man's penance for sleeping with a woman in the god's sanctuary.

Reference: al-Şilwī 1

Reference: FB-wādī Shuḍayf 2

Reference: Haram 40

Reference: MŞM 7250

Reference: al-Şilwī 3

Reference: Haram 35

Reference: Haram 33

Reference: RES 2803

Reference: MB 2005 I-88

Reference: München 94-317880

Reference: Haram 34

Reference: RES 4176

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals know that the cause of punishment is divine. However, they do not necessarily know which god(dess) they have angered or what is the reason for the anger, which may be ascertained by asking a series of binary questions to the oracle. The presently unpublished Mon.script.sab. 76 is a divinatory text in which an individual attempts to narrow down which divinity has brought about his illness.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done randomly:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: They are emphasized as penalties and mentioned in penitential text. But, most South Arabian text concentrate on acquiring future blessing from the deities rather than avoiding punishment.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes
 - Notes: For instance, see the text Ja 2361, which pronounces curse upon the individual who transgresses a boundary and his descendants.
 - Reference: Ja 2361
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: "Good luck" is a common blessing requested by dedicants, especially towards the end of the polytheistic period.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals frequently devote various things to the god seeking blessing. Hence, the desire for divine-blessing does cause individuals to engage in devotional activity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Done randomly:
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes
Notes: Dedications frequently appeal to the relevant gods for blessings and protection.
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: Invocations are made against sickness and individuals dedicate to gods for their healing.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Property, mostly livestock, are also entrusted to divinities for their blessing.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Partial sexual restraints are attested in cultic contexts. These usually seem to be concerned with purity. Confer the section about personal hygiene above.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Monogamy (males):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Monogamy (females):

– No

Notes: The oracle MŞM 3634 appears to record a woman who was the wife of two men.

Reference: MŞM 3634

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Children are frequently dedicated to gods but there is never an explicit mention that they were sacrificed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Albeit, individuals did dedicate themselves to the gods but not in a suicidal way.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Sacrifice/dedication of valuable property and items, such as inscriptions, land, and children, are commonplace in South Arabian religion. However, whether this was obligatory remains uncertain.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Aside from the sacrifice of time required to prepare offerings, it is uncertain if there were time expectations. Most scholars hypothesize that there were either ḥḍr- or wfr-pilgrimages in this region, albeit I myself am skeptical of these reconstructions, which may better be interpreted as "offerings." There is also evidence for the practice of the ḥagg, which is related to the Islamic Hajj. However, it is uncertain if this was mandatory.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private,

household):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: In the inscriptions RES 4176 and Schm/Sir 92, various groups are informed of their obligation to perform the ḥḍr-ritual (traditionally interpreted as pilgrimage, but most likely a type of seasonal offering) to the Sabaean patron god Almaqah.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: On the road ascending the mountain to the god Ta'lab's sanctuary, an oracle was

engraved in the side of the cliff that provided stipulations for proper cultic practice. At the god Nakrah's sanctuary at Darb aṣ-Ṣabî, an oracle was erected at the entrance of one of the cultic buildings that outlined rules managing the sick, dying, and miscarrying individuals in the sanctuary. The stele YM 28488 contains two oracles, one from the high god 'Athtar dhu-Qabḏ and another from the slightly-lesser ranking Wadd. 'Athtar dhu-Qabḏ's oracle installs the king over distribution of his offerings, while Wadd installs the priests over his offerings. Another seeming oracle, CIH 464, appears to outline the proper practice of the enigmatic ḏqṭ-ritual at what appears to be an oracular sanctuary in Jār al-Labbā.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: The kings of Saba and Qataban will refer to their people collectively as the children of the national god. Hence, the Sabaeans are the "Children of Almaqah" (wld 'Imqḥ) while the Qatabanians are the "Children of 'Amm" (wld 'm).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: It is actually multiple kingdoms or "states," which are frequently referred to as "tribes" by the field.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary of Nakrah̄ at Darb aṣ-Ṣabī had regulations concerning the sick, infirm, and miscarrying individuals, which implies that some care could be provided locally.

Reference: MAFRAY-Darb aṣ-Ṣabī 1

Reference: Christian Robin , Jean-François Breton , Jacques Ryckmans. Le sanctuaire minéen de Nkr̄h à Darb aṣ-Ṣabī (environs de Barâqiš̄). Rapport préliminaire (seconde partie). Étude des inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Priests and other cultic personnel are common in South Arabia.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Local sanctuaries are recorded as having their own water sources. A number of penitential texts concern transgressions against the gods concern manipulating water resources (Fr-Şan'ā' 5, YM 10886, YM 26106)

Reference: YM 26106

Reference: YM 10886

Reference: Fr-Şan'ā' 5

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

— Yes

Notes: In CIH 338, a local cultic official records repairing the "road of the mountain" (w-ʿḡb ms'lb' ʿrn) that leads up to the sanctuary of Ta'lab.

Reference: CIH 338

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

— Yes

Reference: Alexander Sima. Notes on ʿšr in Sabaeen inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Reference: Jason Weimar. Taxation and public labour in ancient Saba': an examination of ḥrṣ using the Leiden and Munich minuscule inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: In MB 2002 I-28, the god Almaqah orders a sentence of death for certain cultic transgressions.

Reference: MB 2002 I-28

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: An instance of this is the inscription Robin/al-Mašamayn 1, which proclaims that anyone who washes an animal in a sacred cistern will be struck fifty times.

Reference: Robin/al-Mašamayn 1

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: MB 2002 I-28 appears to condemn people to death who do not ostracize wrongdoers, implying the wrongdoers are also exiled.

Reference: MB 2002 I-28

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: The most attested method of punishment is through fines.

Reference: MB 2002 I-28

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Various shrines will post local oracular laws for residents and visitors to adhere to.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

— Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Individuals participate in the state's military service, which is defined in religious terminology. For instance, in RES 3945, the king of Saba Karibil Watar identifies his army as the "Children of Almaqah," their kingdom's patron god. Karibil also repeatedly boasts of his conquest being done "for Almaqah and for Saba."

Reference: RES 3945

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Several major month names in Sabaeen calendar are named after divinities, which hints that the calendar was cultic in origin.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The text CIH 563+CIH 956 mentions a priest having comestibles brought from certain territories.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Reference: CIH 563+CIH 956

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

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↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 360 CE

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